

Number Theory Functions Expressed Using Trigonometric Functions and Integrals

Lazar Zlatić
zlaticlazar@gmail.com

Abstract

Utilising the difference between certain discontinuous functions and their Fourier series in the points of discontinuity, this paper presents alternative expressions for some important functions in number theory. Similar results are presented for other number theory functions where the results are achieved by the means of the Z-transform. Also, the usage of such expressions for the purpose of asymptotic analysis is discussed.

The Initial Idea

Consider the function $f(u) = u \bmod p$ for some integer p . We can write the corresponding Fourier series for this function as:

$$f(u) = \frac{p}{2} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{p}{\pi n} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{p}\right) \quad (1)$$

However, the series does not converge to the correct value for those integers u that are divisible by p . In those points $f(u) = 0$, whilst the value of the series is $\frac{p}{2}$. Still, we can consider a sum of such functions:

$$F(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u u \bmod p \quad (2)$$

We can represent this function as the sum of the corresponding Fourier series. However, in order to account for the difference between the function and the series in the points where the modulus is 0, we can subtract $\frac{p}{2}$ for every p that divides u . Thus we arrive at the following expression:

$$F(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u \left(\frac{p}{2} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{p}{\pi n} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{p}\right) \right) - \frac{\sigma(u)}{2} \quad (3)$$

where $\sigma(u)$ represents the sum of the divisors of u .

$$\begin{aligned}
& \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{u \bmod p}{p} - \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{(u-1) \bmod p}{p} = H_u - d(u) \\
& \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{(u-1) \bmod p}{p} - \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{(u-2) \bmod p}{p} = H_u - d(u-1) \\
& \quad \vdots \\
& \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{(u-u+2) \bmod p}{p} - \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{(u-u+1) \bmod p}{p} = H_u - d(2) \\
& \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{(u-u+1) \bmod p}{p} - \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{(u-u) \bmod p}{p} = H_u - d(1)
\end{aligned}$$

where $d(p)$ is the number of the divisors of p , whilst H_u is the sum of the reciprocals of integers up to u , $H_u = \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{1}{p}$, we can formulate the following equation:

$$\sum_{p=1}^u d(p) = uH_u - \sum_{p=1}^u \left(\frac{1}{2} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\pi n} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi n u}{p}\right) \right) + \frac{d(u)}{2} \quad (6)$$

We can also develop the general case for $F(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u p^k (u \bmod p)$, resulting in the equation¹:

$$\sum_{p=1}^u \sigma_k(p) = uH_{u,k} - \sum_{p=1}^u \left(\frac{p^k}{2} - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{p^k}{\pi n} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi n u}{p}\right) \right) + \frac{\sigma_k(u)}{2} \quad (7)$$

where $\sigma_k(u)$ is the sum of the k -th powers of the divisors of u , whilst $H_{u,k} = \sum_{p=1}^u p^{k-1}$.

It may also be of interest to consider what other notable functions can be represented as differences between certain discontinuous functions and their corresponding Fourier series. Also, we can analyse the difference between these functions at two different values as well, producing different trigonometric series. This may be of interest in problems concerning the difference (or the equality) of divisor functions at different points [1], that is the question of when does $\sigma_k(n) = \sigma_k(n+l)$ for some integers n and l .

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The k in this expression can be any real number for the purpose of this paper. However, it might also be of interest to, more broadly, consider complex values as well.

Asymptotic Analysis

Now we can consider using the presented expressions for the purpose of analysing the asymptotic behaviour of the considered functions. Let us begin by considering the sum for $k = 0$, that is for $\sigma_k(u) = d(u)$. Using the known [2] result $H_u = \ln(u) + \gamma + O(1/u)$, where γ is the Euler-Mascheroni constant. We can provide the following expression:

$$\sum_{p=1}^u d(p) = u \ln(u) + u\left(\gamma - \frac{1}{2}\right) + \frac{d(u)}{2} + \sum_{p=1}^u \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\pi n} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{p}\right) + O(1) \quad (8)$$

Let us therefore analyse the term $\sum_{p=1}^u \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\pi n} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{p}\right)$ by replacing the order of the sums and calculating $\sum_{p=1}^u \frac{1}{\pi n} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{p}\right)$ by using Euler-Maclaurin [2] summation:

$$\sum_{p=1}^u \frac{1}{\pi n} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{p}\right) = \frac{1}{\pi n} \left(\int_1^u \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{x}\right) dx - \int_1^u (x - [x]) \frac{2\pi nu}{x^2} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{x}\right) dx \right) \quad (9)$$

We can calculate the first integral, and then use the asymptotic expansion [3] for the trigonometric integral $\text{Ci}(x) = -\int_x^{\infty} \frac{\cos t}{t} dt$, obtained via partial integration, to provide the following evaluation:

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\pi n} \int_1^u \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{x}\right) dx &= 2u \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \text{Ci}(2\pi nu) - 2u \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \text{Ci}(2\pi n) = \\ &= u(-2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \text{Ci}(2\pi n)) + 2u \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} O\left(\frac{1}{n^2 u^2}\right) = uC + O\left(\frac{1}{u}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The constant C in the expression is equal to $\gamma - \frac{1}{2}$, which we can prove by looking at one of the ways [2] to define γ and using the Fourier series of $t - [t]$:

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma &= 1 - \int_1^{\infty} \frac{t - [t]}{t^2} dt = 1 - \int_1^{\infty} \frac{1}{2t^2} dt + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\pi n} \int_1^{\infty} \frac{\sin(2\pi nt)}{t^2} dt \\ &= \frac{1}{2} - 2 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \text{Ci}(2\pi n) = \frac{1}{2} + C \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Thus we can notice that the Dirichlet divisor problem of determining the asymptotic behaviour of $\Delta(u)$, in the expression for the divisor summatory function $\sum_{p=1}^u d(p) = u \ln(u) + u(2\gamma - 1) + \Delta(u)$, is equivalent to determining the asymptotic behaviour of the remaining term:

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{\pi n} \int_1^u (x - [x]) \frac{2\pi n u}{x^2} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n u}{x}\right) dx \quad (12)$$

Now, we can discuss the possible approaches to analysing the integral in the expression. The problem in doing so lies in not being able to further utilize the Euler-Maclaurin formula in the usual way, as it does not produce asymptotically ever smaller remainder terms. Of other possible approaches, we can first try to avoid expanding $x - [x]$ into its Fourier series, and instead notice that by replacing the cosine term in the integral with its Taylor series, we get infinitely many terms, each one corresponding to the remainder term in applying the Euler-Maclaurin formula to calculate sums of the form $\sum_{p=1}^u \frac{1}{p^k}$:

$$\begin{aligned} \int_1^u b(x - [x]) \frac{\cos\left(\frac{b}{x}\right)}{x^2} dx &= b \int_1^u \frac{x - [x]}{x^2} dx - \frac{b^3}{2!} \int_1^u \frac{x - [x]}{x^4} dx + \frac{b^5}{4!} \int_1^u \frac{x - [x]}{x^6} dx - \dots = \\ &= b(\ln(u) + 1 - \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{1}{p}) - \frac{b^3}{3!} \left(\sum_{p=1}^u \frac{1}{p^3} - \frac{1}{u^2}\right) + \frac{b^5}{5!} \left(\sum_{p=1}^u \frac{1}{p^5} - \frac{1}{u^4}\right) - \dots \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $b = 2\pi n u$. These expressions can be progressed further by replacing the sums of the form $\sum_{p=1}^u \frac{1}{p^k}$ with $\sum_{p=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{p^k}$, that is with the corresponding values of the zeta function, subtracting the expression for the addition terms. However, I was not able to find further conclusions as to how to apply these expressions to find the desired asymptotic expansion.

On the other hand, we can also do the replacement of $x - [x]$ with its Fourier series, in order to obtain expressions of the following form:

$$\frac{-1}{\pi n} \int_1^u (x - [x]) \frac{2\pi n u}{x^2} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n u}{x}\right) dx = \frac{1}{\pi n} \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\pi k} \int_1^u \sin(2\pi k x) \frac{2\pi n u}{x^2} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi n u}{x}\right) dx \quad (14)$$

So the current goal can be presented as trying to find some satisfactory expressions concerning the integral:

$$\frac{4u}{ab} \int_1^u \sin(ax) \frac{b}{x^2} \cos\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) dx \quad (15)$$

where $a = 2\pi k$ and $b = 2\pi nu$. Whilst I have found no such expressions, there are some other ways to express the integral in question, which may be of use in finding the results of interest:

$$b \int_1^u \sin(ax) \frac{1}{x^2} \cos\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) dx = a \int_{\frac{b}{au}}^{\frac{b}{a}} \sin\left(\frac{b}{t}\right) \cos(at) dt \quad (16)$$

$$b \int_1^u \sin(ax) \frac{1}{x^2} \cos\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) dx = a \int_1^u \sin\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) \cos(ax) dx \quad (17)$$

$$\int_1^u \sin\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) \cos(ax) dx = a \int_1^u x \sin\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) \sin(ax) dx + b \int_1^u \frac{1}{x} \cos\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) \cos(ax) dx \quad (18)$$

$$b \int_1^u \sin(ax) \frac{1}{x^2} \cos\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) dx = \int_0^\infty \cos(t) \sin\left(\frac{abu}{tu+b}\right) dt - \int_0^\infty \cos(t) \sin\left(\frac{ab}{t+b}\right) dt \quad (19)$$

$$a \int_1^u \sin\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) \cos(ax) dx = \int_0^\infty \cos(t) \sin\left(\frac{ab}{t+a}\right) dt - \int_0^\infty \cos(t) \sin\left(\frac{ab}{t+au}\right) dt \quad (20)$$

The first of these expressions (16) is obtained via the substitution $ax = \frac{b}{t}$. The second expression (17) is obtained by turning the product of the trigonometric functions in the first integral into a sum of trigonometric (sine) functions, and then applying the rule in reverse returning to the product, after the following calculation:

$$\begin{aligned} b \int_1^u \frac{1}{x^2} \sin\left(ax \pm \frac{b}{x}\right) dx &= \pm a \int_1^u \sin\left(ax \pm \frac{b}{x}\right) dx \mp \int_1^u \left(a \mp \frac{b}{x^2}\right) \sin\left(ax \pm \frac{b}{x}\right) dx = \\ &= \pm a \int_1^u \sin\left(ax \pm \frac{b}{x}\right) dx + 0 \end{aligned} \quad (21)$$

The third expression (18) is obtained via double integration by parts:

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_1^u \cos(ax) \sin\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) dx &= -b(\text{Ci}\left(\frac{b}{u}\right) - \text{Ci}(b)) + \int_1^u (ax \sin(ax) \sin\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) - ab \sin(ax) \text{Ci}\left(\frac{b}{x}\right)) dx = \\
&= a \int_1^u x \sin(ax) \sin\left(\frac{b}{x}\right) dx + b \int_1^u \frac{\cos(ax) \cos\left(\frac{b}{x}\right)}{x} dx
\end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

The fourth expression (19) can be proved by starting from the integrals on the right side of the equation and using substitutions $tu + b = \frac{bu}{x}$ and $t + b = \frac{b}{x}$ for the first and the second integral respectively. In a similar fashion, the final expression (20) can be proved by starting from the integrals on the right side of the equation and using substitutions $t = ax - a$ and $t = ax - au$ for the first and the second integral respectively.

It is also of interest to note, that these two final expressions can be arrived at by expanding one of the trigonometric functions in the original integral into its Taylor series, afterwards calculating, one by one, the integrals corresponding to each of the terms of the series multiplied by the remaining trigonometric function (the one that was not expanded into its Taylor series), and finally noticing that the resulting solutions correspond to the trigonometric integral Ci, and the terms obtained in its asymptotic expansion, by repeated partial integration [3], which can then be expressed using the auxiliary functions for the trigonometric integral [4], $f(x) = \int_0^\infty \frac{\sin(t)}{t+x}$ and $g(x) = \int_0^\infty \frac{\cos(t)}{t+x}$, with $\text{Ci}(x) = f(x) \sin(x) - g(x) \cos(x)$, the sum of which results in the final expression. These expressions may prove to be useful, due to endpoints of integration being independent from u . It may also be of interest to discover whether similar expressions can be found by utilising the alternative form of these auxiliary functions, $f(x) = \int_0^\infty \frac{e^{-xt}}{t^2+1}$ and $g(x) = \int_0^\infty \frac{te^{-xt}}{t^2+1}$. Finally, concerning the asymptotic analysis for the sums in the general case $\sum_{p=1}^u \sigma_k(p)$, similar expressions are to be found, with similar problems in trying to produce any concrete results.

Expressions Obtained via Z-Transform

If, instead of the sums of the divisor functions (their average values), we want to consider evaluating the divisor function for some integer u , it is useful to consider the Z-transform [5] for such a function.

Consider for now the sum of the divisors $\sigma(u)$ of some integer u . Let $\delta[u - n]$ be the discrete unit impulse function [5], such that it is equal to 1 if its argument is zero (that is if $u = n$), whilst it is zero for all other inputs. Then we can also

introduce the function $\delta_p[u] = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \delta[u - kp] = \delta[u - p] + \delta[u - 2p] + \delta[u - 3p] + \dots$

Thus the sum of the divisors of u can be written as:

$$\sigma(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u p \delta_p[u] \quad (23)$$

We can then write the Z-transform $X_\sigma(z)$ of the said divisor function as:

$$X_\sigma(z) = \sum_{p=1}^u \frac{p}{1 - z^{-p}} = \frac{z}{z - 1} + \frac{2z^2}{z^2 - 1} + \frac{3z^3}{z^3 - 1} + \dots + \frac{uz^u}{z^u - 1} \quad (24)$$

Then, by calculating the residues corresponding to these terms (which give us certain roots of unity) we can get a new expression for $\sigma(u)$:

$$\sigma(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} e^{i \frac{2\pi uk}{p}} = \sum_{p=1}^u \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi uk}{p}\right) \quad (25)$$

Obtaining this expression, we can notice however, that the use of the Z-transform was not necessary, as we can come to the same conclusion that

$\sigma(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} e^{i \frac{2\pi uk}{p}}$ by looking at the geometric series in the expression,

$\sum_{k=0}^{p-1} e^{i \frac{2\pi uk}{p}}$, and noticing that this sum is equal to zero if p does not divide u and

equal to p (due to all terms in the sum being equal to 1) if p does divide u . The Z-transform may not be complete redundant, however, as in the case of some other function where the result may not be easily obtainable by other means, it may prove fundamentally useful.

To go beyond this individual example, the general expression can be given as:

$$\sigma_m(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u p^{m-1} \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} e^{i \frac{2\pi uk}{p}} \quad (26)$$

where $\sigma_m(u)$ is the sum of the m -th powers of the divisors of u .

To analyse these expressions in the similar fashion as before, we can, again, switch the terms in the sums. On the example of the expression (25) this results

in the following expression:

$$\begin{aligned}
\sigma(u) &= \sum_{p=1}^u \sum_{k=0}^{p-1} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi uk}{p}\right) = \sum_{n=0}^{u-1} \sum_{p=n+1}^u \cos\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{p}\right) = \\
&= u + \sum_{n=1}^{u-1} \left(\int_n^u \cos\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{x}\right) dx + \int_n^u \frac{2\pi nu(x - \lfloor x \rfloor)}{x^2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{x}\right) dx \right) = \\
&= u + \sum_{n=1}^{u-1} (2\pi nu(\text{Si}(2\pi n) - \text{Si}(2\pi u)) + \int_n^u \frac{2\pi nu(x - \lfloor x \rfloor)}{x^2} \sin\left(\frac{2\pi nu}{x}\right) dx)
\end{aligned} \tag{27}$$

where Si is the trigonometric integral $\text{Si}(x) = \int_0^x \frac{\sin t}{t} dt$.

It is of hope that this expression may be used to find evaluations, asymptotic or otherwise, for the divisor sum function.

The Square-Free Version of the Analysis

Previous problems have focused on sums over (all) natural numbers in order. However, it is also of value to consider sums going only over the square-free integers. If we look at the sum of the form:

$$F(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u \mu(p) p^k (u \bmod p) \tag{28}$$

where $\mu(p)$ is the Möbius function [2], we can consider the difference between such sums and the sums of the corresponding Fourier series. In this regard, the only simple case is when $k = -1$, because then, due to there always being an equal number of square-free factors of u having $\mu(p) = 1$ and $\mu(p) = -1$, the corresponding difference is equal to zero.

At this point, it is also of use to consider the functions of the form $F(u) = \sum_{p=1}^u \mu(p) p^k (u^l \bmod p)$, for some real l , as these functions are of use in approaching certain problems from a “sieve method” perspective. For example, the Legendre’s conjecture problem, of whether there is always a prime number between squares of two consecutive integers, can be represented by looking at the differences of such functions at points of u and $u + 1$, for $k = -1$ and $l = 2$:

$$\sum_{p=1}^u \mu(p) \left(\frac{(u+1)^2 \bmod p}{p} - \frac{u^2 \bmod p}{p} \right) \tag{29}$$

The Fourier series of $\frac{u^2 \bmod p}{p}$ and $\frac{(u+1)^2 \bmod p}{p}$ are more complicated than the ones for the similar problem of $\frac{(u \bmod p)^2}{p}$ and $\frac{((u+1) \bmod p)^2}{p}$, however the subtraction in the expression (29) simplifies the problem.

Final Remarks

A method was presented, of expressing certain functions of importance in number theory by using the difference between certain discontinuous functions and their corresponding Fourier series. The potential for asymptotic analysis is also discussed, resulting in the problem of determining the ways for evaluating or providing asymptotic bounds for certain integrals involving trigonometric functions.

Besides the presented results there are some other notable problems, where a possibility exists for the use of the presented method to create expressions of the similar nature and investigate their use for the purpose of asymptotic analysis. These include, besides the mentioned problems of determining the possible values of the differences between divisor functions for different input values and the Legendre's conjecture, the problem of determining the number of lattice points in a circle and, in the square-free case, the problem of determining the number of square-free integers between 1 and some other number. However, the mentioned problems, present further complications, either to the initial posing of the equations, or to an already difficult question of the direction of further progress for the purpose of evaluating the resulting trigonometric expressions.

It is also of interest to consider what other discontinuous functions might be useful for analysis in the sense of utilising the difference between theirs and the values of their corresponding Fourier series at certain points.

References

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